

POTENTIALS FOR SURGICAL URBANISM: A CASE STUDY FOR DOWNTOWN SÃO PAULO

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ABSTRACT

São Paulo is a local metropolis in a global world characterized by continuous fluctuations and constant reconstruction through “a painful process of historical negation,” a territorial and polynucleated palimpsest where the new overrides the already existing in a tireless manner.¹ Such cycles of renewal and rebuilding propitiated the expansion of the city from a small, modest Jesuit mission to the second largest metropolis in the world with a population of around 20 million.² Yet the absence of historical traces of the past sets up a scenario of premature aging described by French anthropologist Claude Lévi-Strauss as “[passing] from freshness to decay without simply being old.”³ However, it is not only the physical appearance of the city that is in constant flux, but also its social composition. The urban development of São Paulo is thus tangled in an unresolved paradox: while the metropolis continues to sprawl uncontrollably onto non-structured peripheral lands through informal settlements, the built historical center undergoes severe degradation and is left with an overabundance of infrastructure and underutilized buildings awaiting reimagination. Is it possible to perform

1. RIO, Vincente Del; WILLIAM J. Siembieda. *Contemporary Urbanism in Brazil: Beyond Brasilia*. Gainesville, University Press of Florida, 2010. p. 248.

2. United Nations Population Division. *World Urbanization Prospects: The 2001 Revision*, p. 11.

3. ANDREOLI, Elisabetta; FORTY, Adrian. *Brazil's Modern Architecture*. London, Phaidon, 2004. p. 12.

surgical operations on these abandoned structures to create a city not based on prescriptive zoning and programming, but rather resilient structures in constant flux that adapts to the needs of its citizens and one that invites customization and participation? This research expresses critical reflections regarding preservations, reuse and restorations involving the transformation of architectural and urban sites in the historical downtown of São Paulo, and proposes for a new city manifesto that employs adaptive reuse as an opportunity to initiate a bottom-up, participatory development of the urban context.

Keywords: São Paulo Downtown, Building Vacancy, Obsolescence, Reoccupation, Bottom-up Urbanism.

POTENCIAS PARA O URBANISMO CIRÚRGICO: UM ESTUDO DE CASO PARA O CENTRO DE SÃO PAULO RESUMO

São Paulo é uma metrópole local em um mundo global caracterizada por flutuações contínuas e uma constante reconstrução através de “um doloroso processo de negação histórica”, um palimpsesto territorial e polinucleado onde o novo substitui o já existente de forma incansável. Tais ciclos de renovação e reconstrução propiciaram a expansão da cidade de uma pequena e modesta missão jesuíta para a segunda maior metrópole do mundo com uma população de cerca de 20 milhões. No entanto, a ausência de vestígios históricos do passado configura um cenário de envelhecimento prematuro descrito pelo antropólogo francês Claude Lévi-Strauss como “passar de frescura a decadência sem simplesmente ser velho”. Porém, não é apenas a aparência física da cidade que está em constante fluxo, mas também sua composição social. O desenvolvimento urbano de São Paulo está, assim, emaranhado em um paradoxo não resolvido: enquanto a metrópole continua a se espalhar incontrolavelmente em terras periféricas não-estruturadas através de assentamentos informais, o centro histórico construído sofre severa degradação e é deixado com uma superabundância de infra-estrutura e edifícios subutilizados à espera Reimaginação. É possível realizar operações cirúrgicas nessas estruturas

abandonadas para criar uma cidade que não se baseie em zoneamento e programação prescritivos, mas sim em estruturas flexíveis em constante fluxo e que se adaptam às necessidades de seus cidadãos e que convidem à personalização e participação? Esta pesquisa expressa reflexões críticas sobre preservação, reuso e restaurações envolvendo a transformação de sítios arquitetônicos e urbanos no centro histórico de São Paulo e propõe um novo manifesto da cidade que utiliza a reutilização adaptativa como oportunidade para iniciar um desenvolvimento participativo de baixo para cima do context urbano.

Palavras-chave: São Paulo Centro, Construção Vaga, Obsolescência, Reocupação, Bottom-up Urbanismo

POTENCIALES PARA EL URBANISMO QUIRÚRGICO: ESTUDIO DE CASO EN EL CENTRO DE SÃO PAULO RESUMEN

São Paulo es una metrópolis local en un mundo global caracterizado por continuas fluctuaciones y constante reconstrucción debido a "un doloroso proceso de negación histórica", un palimpsesto territorial y multinucleado donde lo nuevo supera a lo existente de manera incansable. Tales ciclos de renovación y reconstrucción propiciaron la expansión de esta ciudad de una pequeña y modesta misión jesuita a la segunda metrópolis más grande del mundo, con una población de casi 20 millones. Sin embargo, la ausencia de rastros históricos establece un escenario de envejecimiento prematuro descrito por el antropólogo francés Claude Lévi-Strauss como "el paso de la frescura a la decadencia sin ser simplemente viejo". Sin embargo, no es sólo la apariencia física de la ciudad la que está en flujo constante, sino también su composición social. Por consiguiente, el desarrollo urbano de São Paulo está enredado en una paradoja no resuelta: mientras la metrópolis continúa extendiéndose incontrolablemente sobre tierras periféricas a través de asentamientos informales, el centro histórico existente sufre una degradación severa y queda atrás con una sobreabundancia de infraestructura y edificios infrautilizados, esperando ser reimaginados. ¿Es posible llevar a cabo operaciones quirúrgicas en estas estructuras

abandonadas para crear una ciudad no basada en la zonificación y programación normativa: estructuras resistentes en constante flujo que puedan adaptarse a las necesidades de sus ciudadanos y que inviten personalización y participación? Esta investigación expresa reflexiones críticas sobre preservaciones, reutilizaciones y restauraciones que involucran la transformación de sitios arquitectónicos y urbanos en el centro histórico de São Paulo y propone un nuevo manifiesto de la ciudad que emplea la reutilización adaptativa como una oportunidad para iniciar un desarrollo participativo de abajo hacia arriba dentro del contexto urbano.

Palabras llave: São Paulo Centro, Desocupación de Edificios, Obsolescencia, Reocupación, Urbanismo de abajo hacia arriba.

BRAZILIAN MODERN ARCHITECTURAL HERITAGE AND CULTURAL ATTITUDES

The robustness and immense international influence of Brazilian architecture designed and built between 1920s to 1970s distinguishes Brazilian modernism from its European ancestor. Described as “both Brazilian and universal” by Lauro Cavalcanti in his book *When Brazil Was Modern*, Brazilian modernist architectural heritage is a summation of the country’s economic might and prosperity at the time and the prolific contribution of a “brilliant generation of architects and intellectuals with ties to the cultural apparatus of the state, [which] transformed the style into a new language.”⁴ The modernists exerted their voice and dominance by undertaking control of the Portuguese architectural legacy of the past and by directing design of public housing and planning of the burgeoning urban centers in Brazil, providing functional solutions to social problems in addition to inventing superior architectural languages and forms. The heroic inheritance of this period produced a unique cultural attitude towards architecture and the concept of newness— there can be no such thing as *new Brazilian architecture* because all Brazilian architecture since 1936 is *new*.⁵ Categorizing works post this period automatically shoves the triumphant eras of 1940’s and 50’s into the chasm of obsolescence and “oldness” since oldness is not distinguished from derelict or obsolete. Such attitude is a double-edged sword: while buildings designed by famed masters rest in everlasting newness and celebration, works born out of more humble and anonymous roots tumble into deterioration by default.

URBAN DEVELOPMENT OF SÃO PAULO

In the case of São Paulo, the city is a local metropolis in a global world characterized by continuous fluctuations and constant reconstruction through *a painful process of historical negation*, a territorial and polynucleated palimpsest where the new overrides the already existing in a tireless manner.⁶ Such cycles of renewal and rebuilding propitiated the expansion of the city from a small, modest Jesuit mission to the second largest metropolis in the world with a population

4. CAVALCANTI, Lauro. *When Brazil Was Modern: Guide to Architecture, 1928-1960*. p. 13.

5. ANDREOLI, Elisabetta; FORTY, Adrian. *Brazil's Modern Architecture*. p. 14.

6. *Rio, Contemporary Urbanism in Brazil: Beyond Brasilia*, p. 248.

of around 20 million.⁷ Yet the absence of traces of the past sets up a scenario of premature aging described by French anthropologist Claude Lévi-Strauss as “[passing] from freshness to decay without simply being old.”⁸ However, it is not only the physical appearance of the city that is in constant flux, but also its social and racial composition. Up until recently, the accelerated growth in population in São Paulo establishes a centrifugal implosion, as the city takes up more and more land, it occupies it at lower and lower densities.⁹

The urban development of São Paulo is thus entangled in an unresolved paradox: while the metropolis continues to sprawl uncontrollably onto non-structured peripheral lands through informal settlements, the built historical center undergoes severe degradation and is left with an overabundance of infrastructure and underutilized buildings awaiting reimagination. This process of simultaneous growth and contraction engenders vicious cycles of migration of people to favelas and relocation of businesses and commerce from downtown areas to new districts far removed from the city center. Within the urban context, the relentless process of verticalization requires a re-examination of its morphological and social effects, including shortage of low-income housing yet large percentage of building vacancy, social segregation, excessive privatization of open public space and severe environmental damages.¹⁰ The Map of Social Exclusion indicates discrepancies in standards of living in São Paulo's segregated districts, noting an emptying of regulated formal city towards the unregulated informal outskirts.¹¹

Among the biggest contradictions of the city, although the Greater São Paulo Metropolitan generates more than 25% of the country's gross national product, few efforts have been put into regenerating deteriorated downtown urban spaces.¹² São Paulo is by no means a city for pedestrians; the clogging of traffic, heavy weaving of highways and freeways through its center, as well as dearth of public transport and impossible distances between points of interest render poor mobility to be one of the most crucial civic concerns. Characterized by vacant lots,

7. United Nations Population Division. *World Urbanization Prospects: The 2001 Revision*, p. 11.

8. ANDREOLI; FORTY. *Op. cit.*, p. 12.

9. *Idem*, *ibidem*, p.132.

10. Rio. *Op. cit.*, p. 102.

11. ANDREOLI; FORTY. *Op. cit.*, p. 135.

12. Rio. *Op. cit.*, p. 246.

urban dysfunctions, and concerns of safety, the deteriorating downtown of São Paulo is troubled by low-quality public spaces and an overall lack of urban consciousness.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

This research and design investigation aims to tackle these problematic and contradictory urbanistic issues in São Paulo through designing surgical acupuncture at both an architectural and urban scale in order to recuperate the value of vacated urban areas in the old city center and to express critical reflections regarding preservations, reuse and restorations involving the transformations of architectural and urban sites in the historical downtown of São Paulo. The proposal speculates a new city manifesto that employs adaptive reuse as an opportunity to initiate a bottom-up, participatory development of the urban context, and aims to address the following questions. In a broader framework, what happens to architecture when it has fallen into disuse and irrelevance? Can abandoned architectural and infrastructural sites be rescued from shameful statuses of neglect and have the potential to be preserved, repurposed, celebrated and eventually be beneficial to their surrounding urban fabrics? More specifically to the scenario in São Paulo, can local actions influence a metropolitan territory? Can design at the architectural scale have greater impacts on an urban level in order to resist simulacra and homogenization? What should be considered for the requalification of vacant buildings to fulfill needs and interests of the community and investors alike for this area? And finally, how does urbanism, without simply becoming prescriptive ordering and instrument of repression, confront re-articulation of a fragmented urban territory and embrace an alternative grassroots and participatory model of development rooted in change, uncertainty and incompleteness?

BUILDING VACANCY AND ABANDONMENT IN HISTORICAL DOWNTOWN OF SÃO PAULO. THE PHENOMENON OF A SHRINKING CENTER AND THE SOUTHWEST VECTOR OF DEVELOPMENT

The deterioration of the inner city is largely due to the *frontier mentality* in terms of land consumption described in the previous section. Old centers are vacated when new ones are built; they then become increasingly plagued by rising security and safety concerns as well as corrosion

of desirable public spaces. In a phenomenon known as the *Southwest Vector of Development*, São Paulo's urban expansion experiences a fast-paced, progressive depletive relocation of prestigious office spaces and upper class residential buildings from downtown to the southwestern region along Marginal Pinheiros.¹³ As businesses constantly seek out "new investment opportunities made available by existence of cheap land and sustained by regulations favorable to redevelopment at high densities,"¹⁴ creation of new city centers such as the Paulista Avenue area in the 1950's to later the Higienópolis marks the transference of interest away from the historical downtown. Yet these new commercial cores lack in historical and cultural relevance and exclude a large portion of the population.

This research focuses on opportunities of reoccupying vacant structures in the historical districts of Sé and República, which include both public and private properties mostly constructed between 1920's to 1970's. Mainly administrative and commercial, the Sé and República districts today remain one of the central financial districts of the city despite their deteriorated physical conditions, where urbanity has been molded in accordance to a vertical modernist development. Collapse of the public transport system as well as the cultural mentality of the *Paulistas* both served to precipitate the dire urban decay. The road system implemented in previous decades failed to anticipate the rapid population growth to 5 million people, rendering buildings in the center to be inaccessible for new businesses and living purposes, yet the development of public transport has been stifled due to the immense influence of the self-interested automobile industry.¹⁵ Meanwhile, the mentality of the citizens has altered in parallel with the former scenario. The *Paulistas* aligned their aspirations much with the American consumerist way of life. The use of car has become a crucial mobile necessity besides being a status symbol.¹⁶ A context without rudimentary accessibility to car-parking was no longer socially acceptable.

In terms of public space, in the book *Brazil's Modern Architecture*, author Elisabetta Andreoli criticizes the public domain built by the Paulista bourgeoisie as "one that is badly designed, [exploiting] occupation to the [fullest] and is the result of altering legislation to obtain bigger profits...

13. SHIEH, Leonardo. *Urban Acupuncture as a strategy for São Paulo*. p. 38.

14. ANDREOLI; FORTY. Op. cit., p. 136.

15. MONFREGOLA, Alessandro. *Vacant buildings for housing in São Paulo: How to attract inhabitants and investors in the districts of Se and Republica*. p. 27.

16. Ibid, 27.

[and] meanwhile, increasing violence, the result of a massive degree of social exclusion, [pushing] the wealthy inside their homes, where they are protected by alarms, electric fences, surveillance systems and armies of security guards."¹⁷ More than ever, rethinking urbanism and the creation of productive public space marks a new fundamental praxis in the rehabilitation of the central city.

FACTS AND FIGURES

According to IGBE Census 2010, despite having a broad range of infrastructures, public facilities and jobs, the Sé subprefecture is the least populated administrative region in the city, covering an area of 26.2 km² and having merely 41 106 inhabitants.¹⁸ As of 2005, there are recorded 402 807 vacant houses and flats in São Paulo,¹⁹ and the amount of vacant properties in downtown including both lots and buildings numbers at 523.²⁰ Half of the vacant properties remains to be unidentified. The other half points out that the phenomenon of idleness occurs mainly between properties of commercial use (34.0%), residential use (2.9%) and mixed use (11.1%).²¹ Empirical survey on use of these properties demonstrates the current chief usage of these buildings as parking (44.9%).²² Totally vacant buildings account for 20% of the surveyed properties, and buildings with only the ground floor occupied with commercial activities makes up another 20%.²³

What emerges from this empirical analysis is that the enormous use of the street level for commercial activity and carparking reflects an urban liveliness and a large opportunity for redevelopment. While the street level activities ensure an economic viability of the area, high-rise buildings with 85-90% of vacancy remains an untapped potentiality to reverse the physical depreciation of the property and to reinject possibilities into an enervating urban body.

17. ANDREOLI; FORTY. Op. cit., p. 136.

18. IGBE Census 2010 <http://censo2010.ibge.gov.br/>

19. ROLNIK, Raquel, São Paulo zwischen Wachstum und Schrumpfung. Eine chronologische Stadtgeschichte, *Arch+*, n.190, 2008

20. MONFREGOLA, Alessandro. Vacant Buildings For Housing in São Paulo: How To Attract Inhabitants and Investors in The Districts of Sé and República, p. 40.

21. Ibid, p. 40.

22. Ibid.

23. Ibid..

CURRENT TRENDS OF REOCCUPATION, PROBLEMS OF HOUSING DEFICIT AND ILLEGAL SQUATTER SETTLEMENTS

A contradiction born out of São Paulo's simultaneous urban contraction and peripheral expansion is the lack of low-income housing in a context of urban vacancy and abandonment. The downtown area is characterized by an infrastructural abundance that contrasts with scarcity of housing, with the latter contributing to a growing gap in social inequality and wealth distribution.

The unchecked and overlooked vacant urban terrain becomes free ground for parasitic informal colonization. Since the 1970s, the old city has observed a wide spread of informal economy fraught with street vendors and illegal activities appropriating public spaces in an uncontrolled and disorganized way.²⁴ Subversively, the underprivileged class in society found ways to encroach and inhabit existing architecture and infrastructure to exert its rights to basic needs for shelter and freedom of expression. Self-construction becomes key connivance in addressing the immediate need for housing in the city center. As a prime example, once proudly stood as São Paulo's tallest skyscraper, Edifício São Vito has been expropriated and evacuated in 2004²⁵ and has since been overtaken by squatters.

CURRENT SCENARIO: REOCCUPATION FOR LOW-INCOME HOUSING PURPOSES

In recent years, municipal authorities and banks have initiated endeavors to reverse the decline of the city center as a strategy to contain informal urban sprawl. Conversion of disused industrial buildings to cultural uses, as well as renovation of historic buildings are implemented as attempts to lure investors back into the central areas.²⁶ The modernist *blank-slate* or *tabula rasa* approach to urban design no longer provides solutions to our contemporary urban problems. Rather, providing new functionality and livelihood to decrepit spaces of obsolescence is now the preferred alternative towards planning and design. In a broader sense, the challenge to contemporary architecture

24. Rio. Op. cit., p. 252.

25. Um futuro colorido para o São Vito. *Época*. 19 July 2010.

26. ANDREOLI; FORTY. Op. cit., p. 137.

and urbanism is not to create brand new infrastructures, but rather to confront the existing city, which begins with its infrastructure, without negating it. Instead of trespassing onto satellite, unexplored territories in the peripheries, recent emergence of interest in considering reconversion of buildings as an apt solution to shortages of housing, in light of socio-demographic alterations in the city, would better propel revitalization given the great number of vacancy, current social and cultural dynamics, and the political-legislative context.

We inhabit a moment in time where there is a little room in urban design for “experimentation or for post-modernization of historic facades, fake place-making, and irresponsible gentrification.”²⁷ Rather than superfluous expressions, urbanism ought to be steered by essential needs of the community and the people. Parallel to the shift in attitudes and planning direction undertaken by the official government, grassroots actions taken by community-based, non-governmental organizations to systematically reoccupy abandoned structures as sites for housing exemplify bottom-up endeavors to reclaim socially responsible and programmatic possibilities of these vacant buildings. Housing movements organized by special-interest groups such as *Frente da Luta por Moradia - FLM*, or Front of the Line Housing Struggle aims at urban reform through conversion of useless structures for housing purposes.²⁸

A SPECULATIVE ARCHITECTURAL MANIFESTO. SPATIAL AGENCY, TERRAIN VAGUE AND INDETERMINATE DESIGN

In our current discourse, architecture and urbanism experience a slow shift from a model of timelessness to a model of timeliness. Emergent topics such as *ecological urbanism*, *landscape urbanism*, and *infrastructural urbanism* suggest there is a transition in our operating strategies from deterministic and inflexible systems at the scale of self-referential buildings to adaptable models which include dimensions of temporality and anticipation for change to allow for diversification and customization at the scale of cities. While growth of informal development is mostly frowned upon by authorities, the notion of a participatory planning and grassroots politics developed outside of conventional regulatory frameworks imparts insightful and ingenious solutions to urban problems.

27 Rio. Op. cit., p. 252.

28. Frente de Luta por Moradia. Princípios.

In his research on the developments of African cities such as Lagos, Rem Koolhaas describes their working mechanisms as “mutating operations and adopting agents that would be considered *marginal, liminal, informal or illegal*”.²⁹ In between the rigidity of the utterly prescribed planning reflecting the status quo of São Paulo's formal city and the stark opposite of an anarchistic, self-constructed development mirroring the city's outskirts, lies a sweet balance that embodies the benefits of both. Flexibility in urban design is achieved by negotiating between imposed limits of top-down planning and simultaneous permissions for bottom-up, circumstantial adaptations that respond to unexpected changes.

In his book, *Spatial Agency: Other Ways of Doing Architecture*, Jeremy Till quotes Henri Lefebvre's ideas about social space: “Social space is a social product.”³⁰ A different understanding of space arises out of Lefebvre's redefinition: social production is a “shared enterprise,” and social space is a “dynamic space... [whose] production continues overtime and is not fixed to a single moment of completion.”³¹ Till argues in the spirit of Cedric Price that building is not necessarily the best and only solution to a spatial problem. An alternative way of seeing architecture is one that removes the architect as the individual hero and replaces him with collaborating agents who act with, and on behalf of, others.

Similar idea of embracing indeterminacy has also been proposed by Ignasi de Sola-Morales in his essay *Terrain Vague*, written in 1995. Sola-Morales argues that void and absence a terrain vague is also “promise, the space of the possible, of expectation.”³² The dual concept of a land defined by indeterminacy theorizes on non-design and the margins of the ordered world we are part of. The potential of exploring the concept of terrain vague in design presents a unique chance of imbuing spatial and social form to an existing urban phenomenon of change and uncertainty.

SURGICAL ACUPUNCTURES AS CONSTRUCTED NARRATIVES

The design manifesto portion of this investigation is unlike most architectural manifestos which operate at massive and intangible urban scales, but rather focuses on acupunctural insertions that begin with a

29. ASKAN, Esra. *Reading the Generic City*. p. 144-152.

30. AWAN, Nishat, Tatjana S.; TILL, J. *Spatial Agency: Other Ways of Doing Architecture*, p. 29.

31. *Ibid.*

32. SOLA-MORALES, Ignasi de. *Terrain Vague: Interstices At the Edge of the Pale*. p. 121.

seeded action at the scale of architecture that would then catalyze a series of temporally successive events and grassroots developments involving active participation of the occupants. In addition to the already-existing housing and reoccupation movements, this research and design proposes for the potentiality of expanding on the notion of preservation and reoccupation to greater boundaries by establishing an urban framework for bottom-up, grassroots development in site-specific, programmatically unique yet flexible contexts. Eight narratives, each with its theme extracted from existing cultural and infrastructural contexts, are sited in vacant buildings across downtown to form a constellation of surgical deployments that effectuates a new mobile network of connections rooted in an adaptive and participatory urbanism.

Exploring concepts of spatial agency, terrain vague and indeterminate design discussed in the previous sub-section, each intervention is initially composed of a *half-design* that allows room for future adaptive additions or subtractions related to topics such as community-building, living, food production, mobility, health and the cleansing of water. In each scenario, architecture extends beyond its immediate, restricted plot and relates to a broader context of existing infrastructures such as highways, roads, public open plazas, or green spaces in the city. Names reflecting a theme extracted from existing cultural and infrastructural contexts have been assigned to these new developments, which suggest, but without limiting hybridized programmatic usage of these obsolete structures.

This list of names includes, *starting a protest, where everyone comes from somewhere else, close to water, more than an oasis, for catching a scent, an endless loop, showing off a talent, and a useless void*. These projects are imagined to be developed in parallel with current housing movements such as FLM mentioned in the previous section. To prevent market economy from encroaching into these movements, new suggestions of alternative ownerships in the city such as community-based land trusts, collective ownership or community-based land trust allows such imaginative narratives to be plausible.

In a sequential narrative development, the manifesto starts with a protest, and occupies a vacant office building facing the gate of downtown in front of Viaduto do Cha. The top row of drawings in Figure 3 suggests the very first move that is taken as a initiator. Each *seed* is imbued with indeterminacy yet an overall structure. Absence of limit precisely contains the expectations of mobility and vacant roving. The bottom drawings of Figure 3 are potential temporal developments when the seeds have fully blossomed and matured.

São Paulo's modernist legacy immensely influenced the modernization and rapid development of the city. However, in the light of the status quo, philosophies and methods of urban design from the past eras are no longer applicable in solving our contemporary issues today.

São Paulo's contradictory scenario of a shrinking center and an expanding precarious periphery invites reimagination of architecture's role as programmatic and opportunistic infrastructure that catalyzes seeded events and grassroots developments which eventually gives the city back to its citizens. Ultimately, a new city is overlay onto the old, where incremental changes are allowed in a participatory manner of its occupants, in stark contrast with the concrete jungle the São Paulo as we know today.

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